

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF IDIOMS REFLECTING CHARACTER TRAITS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the linguistic and cultural characteristics of phraseological units in Uzbek and English that express various aspects of human character. Phraseological units are important linguistic elements that reflect a nation's culture, mentality, and historical experience. The study provides a comparative analysis of the semantic similarities and differences of phraseological units in these languages, as well as their national characteristics. Additionally, the article discusses the role of phraseological units in describing human character and examines their linguistic and cultural aspects. The aim of the research is to study the phraseological units that represent different aspects of human character in Uzbek and English from a linguistic and cultural perspective, to analyze their similarities and differences, and to determine how cultural and national thinking is reflected in all three languages. The article describes concepts that shape people's worldview through phraseological units related to human character traits and conducts a comparative analysis of idioms and proverbs that reflect national culture through speech behavior, communication models, and culturally specific symbols. The findings of the study contribute to the examination of the linguistic and cultural aspects of phraseological units that express human character in Uzbek and English, identifying the cultural, historical, psychological, and social factors within them. Moreover, by analyzing interlingual similarities and differences, the study enhances the understanding of the phraseological representation of national culture and mentality, revealing both national and universal cultural characteristics.*

Keywords: *phraseological units, linguistic culture, national mentality, human character, comparative analysis.*

Introduction

It is well known that interest in the lifestyles, customs, values, and traditions of foreign nations has existed since ancient times. Today, relations between countries are increasingly supported through growing international interactions. The success of these interactions largely depends on the ability of individuals from different cultural backgrounds to understand one another correctly. One of the effective ways to study the worldviews of Uzbek and English peoples, including their similarities and differences in perceiving reality, is to compare their languages—particularly by analyzing phraseological units that reflect personal characteristics.

In global linguistics, increasing attention is being given to the interpretation of linguistic units that express human character based on the linguistic worldview, national character, national culture and color, moral norms, mentality, and socio-cultural relations. The phraseology of each language plays a unique role in shaping the figurative representation of the world. Although linguistic imagery reflected in phraseological systems represents a national perspective on the world, it is also based on universal logical-psychological principles and the unique linguistic

foundations of the language. The use of such phraseological units helps reveal the mechanisms of figurative thinking and uncover the immanent linguistic laws that define the nature of language as a system of signs. These laws are independent of social, cultural, or historical factors yet influence the structure, development, and functioning of language. In this regard, one of the key methods of our research is linguistic and cultural analysis. There are many commonalities in the phraseology of different languages because phraseology reflects universal human concepts and attitudes toward the world. At the same time, many phraseological units are distinguished by their national characteristics. These differences manifest in the nuances of phraseological meanings, their national imagery, and their lexical composition.

All languages are rich in set expressions. Since ancient times, idioms, similes, proverbs, and aphorisms have held a significant place in both spoken language and written literature. Phraseological expressions have great stylistic potential, making them more expressive and impactful than other lexical tools. Extensive research has been conducted—and continues to be conducted—on the emergence, development, and semantic, grammatical, and functional evolution of phraseological units in global linguistics.

Literature analysis and methodology

Among the scholars who have made substantial contributions to this field in Russian linguistics, the works of V.V. Vinogradov, A.V. Kunin, N.N. Amosova, I.I. Chernisheva, A.M. Babkin, I.V. Arnold, V.L. Arkhangelsky, B.A. Larin, and N.M. Shansky are particularly noteworthy. In Western linguistics, the studies of Charles Bally on phraseological analysis have been of great significance. Later, researchers such as A. Cowie, J. Firth, and J. Sinclair further developed and substantiated these ideas in their studies on the semantics of phraseological units.

In Uzbek linguistics, numerous dissertations have been defended, scientific articles published, monographs and textbooks issued, and phraseological dictionaries compiled on the scientific and practical study of phraseological units. The foundations of Uzbek phraseology have been deeply explored in the research of scholars such as Ye.D. Polivanov, Sh. Rahmatullayev, Ya.D. Pinkhasov, M. Umarxodjayev, A. Mamatov, B. Yuldoshev, A. Isayev, M. Sodiqova, Q. Hakimov, Sh. Usmonova, K. Bozorboev, B. Joraeva, Sh. Abdullayev, Sh. Almamatova, M. Vafoeva, and others [Yuldoshev 2017].

Recent foreign studies in this field include research by H. Ali, A. Saleem, and I. Ullah, which focuses on the pragmatic analysis of proverbs related to courage and honor in Pashto and English [Ali, Saleem, Ullah 2023]. Another study by V. Hanke, J. Karlsson, S. Poulsen, and E. Vindbjerg examines how Arabic-speaking patients understand and verbally express depression [Hanke, Carlsson, Poulsen, Vindbjerg 2022]. V. Nyamandi's research investigates metaphors related to "aging" and "old age" used among Zimbabweans, considering the length of their stay in the United States [Nyamandi 2023]. P. Sean Rivera's study explores the metonymies used to describe the physical appearance of Mexicans and Irish people in America [Rivera 2021]. B.T. Al-Otaibi's research, titled "The Problem of Translational Equivalence of Political Phraseological Units in Russian and Arabic Newspaper Discourse," analyzes the translation equivalence of political phraseological units in Russian and Arabic newspaper texts and their functioning in both languages [Al-Otaibi 2023]. Additionally, the works of scholars such as V.N. Teliya [Teliya 1993], S.G. Ter-Minasova [Ter-Minasova 2008], S.V. Maksimets [Maksimets 2015], P.S. Dronov [Dronov 2018], and A.E. Mamatov [Mamatov 2020] contribute to the study of the linguistic and cultural aspects of phraseology. Furthermore, scientific research on various aspects of

phraseological units that express human character traits includes the works of E.F. Arsentyeva [Arsentyeva 1989], R.Yu. Abdullayeva [Abdullayeva 2021], and other researchers.

In Uzbek linguistics, adjectives, word combinations, phraseological units that reflect human character traits have been thoroughly examined and described. Sh.M. Iskandarova's views on the "microfield of personality" have laid the foundation for anthropocentric research on character traits in the Uzbek language [Iskandarova 1998]. In her dissertation, D.A. Tosheva discusses how words denoting the meaning of "animal" can indicate human character traits [Tosheva 2017]. The research conducted by M. Vafoeva and F.M. Ibragimova is related to linguistic cultural studies and provides well-founded conclusions on the use of Uzbek food and nutrition-related terms in expressing national character [Vafoeva 2009], [Ibragimova 2011]. Z. Sh. Jumayeva has studied the symbolic characteristics of ethno-phraseological units containing components related to food, zoomorphism, clothing, colors, and numbers from a semantic-pragmatic and linguistic-cultural perspective [Jumayeva 2021]. N.F. Tursunova's research focuses on the linguocultural analysis of phraseological units that express national and cultural characteristics in various language systems [Tursunova 2021]. In her study, S.T. Khudoyorova explores the linguistic-cultural and stylistic aspects of phraseological and paremiological units related to historical topics in English and Uzbek [Khudoyorova 2020]. Z. Q. Teshaboeva's research aims to analyze the semantic, componential, and cognitive-conceptual features of phraseological units with national and cultural characteristics in English translations of Baburnama [Khudoyorova 2021]. B. I. Boltayeva's scientific work is dedicated to studying the transformation of phraseological units in the Uzbek language [Boltayeva 2019]. Sh. Q. Shamsiyeva's research focuses on the linguistic-cultural aspects of the formation and sources of euphemisms in Chinese and Uzbek [Shamsiyeva 2018].

Despite the extensive scientific research on the linguistic-cultural aspects of phraseological units over the years, it has been found that phraseological expressions reflecting human character traits have not been sufficiently studied. Additionally, there is a need for an in-depth comparative and linguistic-cultural analysis of such expressions in Uzbek and English, as well as a comprehensive investigation of translation challenges. In line with this issue, the objective of this study is to analyze phraseological units that express human character traits in English and Uzbek from a linguistic-cultural perspective. This research aims to describe the linguistic worldview characteristic of these nations and scientifically substantiate the methods and tools for their translation.

Discussion

Linguocultural analysis is a research method aimed at studying the interrelation between language and culture. Through this approach, the patterns of how language reflects cultural values, stereotypes, mentality, worldview, and national cultural identity are examined. This type of analysis is applied in fields such as linguistics, cultural studies, ethnography, and intercultural communication. A key feature of modern linguistic research is the in-depth study of the national and cultural aspects of languages. In this study, our primary focus is on phraseological units. Phraseological units encapsulate a nation's historical development and cultural heritage within their semantics. They preserve and transmit cultural stereotypes across generations, embedding cultural codes within fixed expressions and revealing the distinctive nature of a particular people.

The semantic analysis of phraseological units plays a key role in their linguocultural study. In semantic analysis, phraseological meaning is classified into positive, negative, and neutral

components, which are based on judgment, approval, or the absence of a strong emotional attitude - reflecting a socially established evaluation of a given phenomenon. Accordingly, phraseological expressions (PEs) describing human character are categorized into three main groups in the compared languages: those with a positive evaluation, those with a negative evaluation, and those with a neutral evaluative meaning. The quantitative distribution of phraseological units across these groups indicates a common pattern and similarity between the phraseological microsystems of English and Uzbek that reflect human character traits. Let us analyze these PEs in more detail from a semantic perspective. The group of PEs expressing negative character traits includes those conveying disapproval as a reflection of a socially established evaluation of certain human qualities. In both Uzbek and English, this is the largest group: in Uzbek, out of a total of 202 PEs, 146 (72%) belong to this category, while in English, out of 799 PEs, 524 (66%) are classified as negative. The predominance of negatively connoted expressions can be explained by the stronger emotional and cognitive reaction of people to negative phenomena. Additionally, in stressful situations—characterized by sharply negative emotional states—there is a natural tendency to rely on pre-formed speech patterns, including set phrases and fixed expressions. Below, we provide examples of PEs from several phraseo-semantic subgroups of negative evaluation:

- **Duplicity, hypocrisy:** a double game; play a double game; show a false face; sail (fight) under (hang out) false colours; shayton yig'i; tili asal, yuragi zahar; paxta qo'yish, pinjiga kirish.
- **Meanness:** a bad actor; swear black is white; paint smb black; yellow dog; false heart; yellow streak; qora yurak; ichi qora; zaharli ilon; tishlolmayman, o'paman
- **Arrogance, conceit:** holier-than-thou; mount (be on, ride, get on) the night horse; proud (vain) as a peacock; proud as Lucifer, high (proud) stomach; o'ziga bini qo'ymoq; o'yog'ini uchida ko'rsatmoq; burni baland.
- **Cruelty, ruthlessness, callousness:** hard heart; cold as charity; cool as cucumber; stony heart; hard as a flint (a stone, the nethermill stone); hard as iron; tosh yurak; diydasi qattiq; gov mehr.
- **Talkativeness, boastfulness:** hot-air artist (merchant); big mouth; a loose (long) tongue; to have a loose (long) tongue; og'zi katta; o'zini ko'rsatmoq; uyda chaksa uni yo'q, tom boshida qo'sh tandir.
- **Greed:** greedy as a wolf; a god beg of a naked man as a miser; tight fist; close liver; cheap skate; besh qo'lini og'ziga tiqmoq; yeb to'ymagan, yalab to'ymaydi; ko'zi och.
- **Impudence, shamelessness:** blush like a black (blue) dog; cool beggar (card, customer, fish, hand); dead to shame; a smart Alec; beti qattiq, terisi qalin; betga chopar.
- **Cunning, flattery:** artful as a art load of monkeys; old fox; sly fox; a tame spaniel; an oily tongue; to have an oily tongue; to be silver-tongued; tricky as a monkey; tricky Nicky; ayyor tulki, ilonning moyini yalagan, shaytonga dars beradi
- **Cowardice:** cold feet; white liver; yellow dog; get (have) cold feet; fly (mount, show) the white feather; (as) timid as a hare; a yellow streak; to be rabbit(pigeon)-hearted; to be fainthearted; to have cold feet, a yellow belly; quyon yurak; soyasidan qo'rqadi; chumchiq pirr etsa, yuragi shirr etadi.
- **Rudeness, lack of restraint, irascibility:** gruff as a bear; hairy about (at, in) the heel (the fetlocks); surly beggar (dog); short temper; rough and tough; rough and tumble; common scold; wild and woolly; a hot head; burnidan eshak qurti tushgan.

- **Sarcastic, prone to gossip:** evil tongues; sharp tongue; bitter tongue; tili zahar; tili bilan yiradi; og'zi bilan qush tutmoq.
- **Stubbornness:** qaysar eshak, bo'yni yo'g'on.
- **Tendency to steal:** to have sticky fingers; to have light fingers; qo'li egri
- **Laziness:** lazy dog; cho'pni u yog'dan bu yoqqa olib qo'ymaydi; nari borsam, xo'kkiz o'lar, beri kelsam arava sinar; arava sinsa, yalqovga o'tin.

The analysis of phraseological expressions (PEs) denoting negative character traits reveals a significant similarity between English and Uzbek PEs, both quantitatively and qualitatively. However, when comparing the volume of phraseology within certain subgroups, some discrepancies become evident. For instance, English has a greater number of PEs in the subgroups of arrogance, madness, stupidity, duplicity, boastfulness, rudeness, impudence, and baseness. Meanwhile, Uzbek features a larger number of PEs in the subgroups of foolishness, envy, ruthlessness, arrogance, gossip, cunning, and laziness.

The group of phraseological expressions (PEs) that express positive character traits includes those that convey approval as a reflection of a socially established evaluation of certain personality traits. Their number is significantly smaller compared to PEs with negative connotations. In English, there are 186 such PEs, accounting for 23% of the total 799 analyzed PEs. In Uzbek, there are 40 PEs, making up 20% of the total 202 identified PEs. Let us examine some specific subgroups of positively connoted PEs individually.

- **Courage, bravery:** high blood; be free of one's flesh; die game; put on a bold front; make the best of a bad job; a strong man; stout heart; bold (brave) as a lion; make the best of a bad bargain (business); make the best of it; as bold as brass; red blood; sher yurak.
- **Sincerity:** single heart (mind); as open as the day; plain dealer; make a clean breast of smth; he is an open book; to be open-hearted; ochiq ko'ngil; yuragida kiri yo'q; ko'ngli bahor.
- **Honesty:** play a straight bat; treat smb white; (as) straight as a die; as honest a man as ever broke bread (as ever lived by bread; as honest a man as ever trod on earth, shoe leather; honest, as honest as the skin between his brows); the clean thing; clean hands; straight goods; straight dealing fair play; kind (honest, simple) soul; clean liver; fair play; tog'ri so'zlik; bir so'zlik; belida belbog'i bor.
- **Diligence, hard work:** a willing horse; (as) busy as a bee (busy as a beehive; as a beaver, as a hen with one chicken; busy as a cockroach on a hot stove; as a one-armed paperhanger); work double tides; work at high pressure; chumoliday ishlaydi; qo'li kosov, sochi supurgi.
- **Nobility, kindness, generosity:** a big heart; a high mind; good as gold; good sport (sort; egg, onion); good as pie; good nature; yuragi daryo; bag'ri keng; yumshoq ko'ngil.
- **Cheerfulness, optimism:** merry as a cricket (grig; a marriage bell, as maids); playful as a kitten; light heart; free liver; cheerful (gay) as a lark; fresh as a daisy (a rose; as paint, as new paint; flowers in may); free and easy; see through rose-coloured glasses; bir qop yong'oq, shaqur-shuqur yong'oq.

The quantitative comparison of phraseological expressions (PEs) denoting positive character traits in English and Uzbek has revealed some distinctive features. It is particularly interesting that the English language contains significantly more PEs in the subgroups of "intelligence," "virtue," "energy," and "activity," whereas in Uzbek, the predominant subgroups are "sincerity," "harmlessness," and "diligence."

The group of phraseological expressions (PEs) with a neutral evaluation of a person's character includes those that lack a distinctly positive or negative connotation. This is the smallest of the three identified PE groups in the compared languages. In English, this group comprises 89 PEs, accounting for 11% of the total expressions selected for the study, while in Uzbek, there are 16 PEs, making up 8% of the total. Some PEs in this category have a consistently neutral meaning, regardless of context. For example: negative virtue - "passive" virtue (describing people who do not cause harm but also do not actively do good); easy game (prey, meat) - a gullible person; по простоте душевной (сердечный) - someone who is naïve, trusting. Other neutral PEs, however, are context-dependent. Their meaning can shift to convey positive or negative connotations based on the surrounding discourse. For example: a queer bird (card, cove, duck) - oydan tushgan- a peculiar or eccentric person; gentle (meek) as a lamb; as mild as a dove (lamb, as May, milk) - qo'uday uyvosh -кроткий как ягненок (овечка)-describing someone who is meek, gentle, or submissive.

Conclusion

Linguocultural analysis methods, which aim to study phraseological units as a means of transmitting cultural knowledge, identify their national characteristics, examine mental structures and their linguistic representation, and explore similarities and differences between languages and cultures, play a crucial role in fostering a deeper understanding of intercultural aspects. These methods are widely applied in translation, foreign language teaching, and the development of educational materials that take cultural context into account.

When analyzing the semantic structure of phraseological units, special attention is given to identifying their metaphorical meaning. Many phraseological units are based on symbols, imagery, and metaphors, conveying deep meanings associated with specific cultural values and perceptions. By comparing and conducting a contrastive analysis of phraseological units across different languages, researchers can determine the similarities and differences in how these expressions are used in various cultures. Studying Uzbek and English phraseological units from a linguocultural perspective helps understand their usage in different communication contexts, the social and cultural information they carry, and how speakers of these languages interact and establish relationships. Additionally, researching the linguocultural aspects of phraseological units allows scholars to draw conclusions about cultural values, moral norms, and ideals inherent in a specific national culture. Moreover, the linguocultural study of phraseological units in Uzbek and English is crucial for intercultural communication, as it facilitates a better understanding of cultural diversity, acknowledges similarities and differences in mentality, and ensures successful information exchange among representatives of different cultures. In conclusion, analyzing phraseological units in these three languages from a linguocultural perspective is an integral part of a comprehensive linguistic study, providing an invaluable tool for understanding and interpreting language phenomena and their cultural manifestations.

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